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**Ethical Challenges Of Election Misinformation In Malaysia's GE15 : A Media
Ethics Perspective**

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Ethical Challenges Of Election Misinformation In Malaysia's GE15 : A Media Ethics Perspective

Abstract

This report aims to discuss the ethical concerns of misinformation dissemination in national elections in Malaysia particularly during the 15th General Election (GE15) from November 2022 to May 2023 and also state election in 2023. This study presents four theories of media ethics which are Ethics of Care, Utilitarianism, Kantian Ethics and Social Responsibility Theory to identify the ethical responsibilities of news outlets, social media and the general public in combating election misinformation through a case study analysis. The study finds that like TikTok, Facebook and Twitter are the main sources of misinformation in Malaysia while the main categories of misinformation are based on economic data, health rumours and emerging deepfake technology against politicians. In the content of misinformation control, the paper examines the regulatory shortcomings after the 2019 repeal of the Anti-Fake News and offers recommendations on media literacy education and AI-generated content regulation to effectively tackle misinformation ethically.

Keywords: Misinformation, Malaysia Elections, Media ethics, Social media, Political, TikTok, Digital Communication.

Background Of The Malaysia's GE15

Today digital technologies have revolutionized how political information is created, shared and received. Political communication on social media, especially TikTok, has emerged as a key means for politicians, journalists and citizens to directly communicate with each other on the digital platforms. These platforms give unpredictable opportunities for political participation, public discourse and democratic engagement. While digital media has also made the dissemination of misinformation very fast especially in election cycles when political information is crucially important for shaping public opinion and voting behaviour. Election misinformation is referred to as the false accusation that has undermined election confidence and has resulted in a national trend of anti-voter bills (Center, B. (2026)). The digital election misinformation differs from traditional misinformation because it can become widespread quickly via social media algorithms, user-generated or online communities to notify the users about the fake information. The fast pace with access to information and the viral character of digital platforms makes it easier to disseminate the fake information to millions of digital audiences within a short timeframe. This makes it challenging for citizens to identify the facts and understand that the information on social media is manipulated or not.

Hence, election misinformation is now a major concern for governments along with the media coverage and the civil society groups across the globe to make sure the trustworthiness of the information that is posted on the digital media. In recent years, the manipulation of false political information such as voter manipulation, political polarization, loss of trust in institutions and also the threats to democratic integrity. The impact of social media in political communication has been seen to rise in Malaysia in the last decades. Electronic media are increasingly being used by political campaigns for voter outreach and to spread campaign messages in order to impact public opinion. With a growing Internet usage and the rise of smart phones, social media has become one of the key channels where many Malaysians get their political updates.

This is especially true regarding Malaysia's Fifteenth General Election (GE15) held on 19 November 2022 (Randall Puah. (2022, November 18)). GE15 was seen as one of the most competitive elections in the nation's history. This election was held in a very digitalised media world in which political parties actively used social media to communicate with voters. Moreover, the introduction of UNDI18 and automatic voter registration increased the voter base and these young voters are mostly digital voters. The misinformation can be about political candidates, government institutions or important social topics when it comes to elections. Hence, election misinformation can have serious consequences for democratic process. If false information is being spread widely, voters could have misconceptions about political candidates or the voting process. This means that misinformation can make voting behaviour to cause a loss of trust in democratic institutions.

Problem Statement

This development of social media has revolutionized political communication in Malaysia. Digital platforms can offer chances to participate in politics and share information but also have become a significant source of misinformation around elections. In Malaysia's GE15, the political parties and citizens engaged in a large amount of political discussion and dissemination of political content on social media platforms. The ease of use of these platforms also allowed for the quick spread of false and misleading information among voters. A significant worry is the potential impact of election misinformation on citizen's capacity to make informed political choices. The misinformation is often shared about sensitive issues like race and political identity in elections. Hence, the voter must know how to identify all these fake news by themselves.

While there has been some research on misinformation and social media use in Malaysia where most were political or technological in nature. The need for an ethical view toward election misinformation, especially in GE15, still exists. Thus this report aims to discuss the ethical issues of election misinformation and examine the roles of the different stakeholders in political communication.

Literature Review

Fake News And Misinformation

With the growing impact of digital media, fake news and misinformation have become a phenomenon in recent years. Both of these words are sometimes interchangeable among the users. Fake news is a type of content that typically appears like real news and includes false or incorrect information. Basically, fake news can be manufactured for political or financial reasons. Misinformation refers to people who can share inaccurate information either when they do not check the information or just post content without careful thought. This means that the misinformation may be shared very quickly without an intent to deceive it. This situation often happens because of the increasing use of social media creating misinformation more easily and accessible. Social media is different from traditional media where only filtered information is available through professional editors and journalists which allows the users to produce and post content. The ecosystem provides a fast track for misinformation to be disseminated with sharing, reposting and forwarding to other users quickly.

Election is a time when citizens actively look for information about politics and there are especially high risks for misinformation. The misrepresentations about the candidate, parties or public policies could highly shape the voter's perceptions. At the same time, this can cause confusion in the public opinion. Therefore, misinformation has always been an important issue in democratic societies throughout the world. It is crucial that the ability to separate between fact and fiction of informed citizenship and identifying the accuracy of information before sharing to others on social media platforms.

Politics In The Digital Age

Political communication is the process of information being communicated between politicians, the news and the public (Direct, S. (2015)). It serves as a significant aspect in the democratic societies which enable the people to receive the information and engage in the political debate. In the past, political communication was traditionally controlled by the newspaper, radio and television that serve as the gatekeepers of information to the public in order to filter and disseminate information before transfer to the traditional media. It is because they want to make sure that the news or the information that is reported out is what they want to let the public receive it. But the new technology of the digital era has made a change on the face of political communication. Social media has made the traditional media by minimized their roles and opened up the new responsibilities for communication between the political actors and the people. Hence, social media successfully became a crucial platform for the political campaign and the political engagement at the same time to reach out to the voters without being limited to newspaper or television networks. Likewise, citizens can actively engage with politics and express their view, comment on the political matters and create their own content.

Social media is a two way street communication unlike the traditional media where the messages are sent from media organisations to audiences. This puts citizens in direct contact with the actors in the political arena and allows them to be more active in public debates. Digital political communication has been growing more influential in Malaysia over the last decade. Smartphones and the increased use of social media have all helped fuel the spread of online political discussion. It is because more political parties have adopted digital platforms to communicate campaign messaging and garner the support among the voters. During GE15, the importance of digital communication became clear. Based on the Council , B. (2022) reported the introduction of Undi18, which is the reduction of voting age from 21 to 18 years old. The automatic voter registration also led to an increased electorate which included many first time voters. As younger voters are among the most engaged with social media and the political campaigns were more likely to focus on digital channels to target this younger audience.

Thus platforms like TikTok, Facebook and Instagram were significant areas for political communication during GE15. The platforms were utilised by political parties, candidates and

citizens to discuss the political issues and share the election related information. This expanded the political participants but it also opened the door to the dissemination of misinformation to voters. Although digital political communication provides great opportunities for more democratic engagement, there are also issues of information quality and ethical responsibility in this context. These are the consideration need to take into account when analysing election misinformation in the Malaysia's GE15

Social Media On Elections

Social media is now one of the most powerful election campaign communication tools around the globe. Digital platforms have become a critical part of political campaigns by providing a way to target a wide audience and engage with voters directly. In some countries, social media can be said that social media is the main source of spreading political information especially for young people. Social media are used in different ways by different political stakeholders during elections, These basically include campaign messaging, mobilizing supporters and encouraging the voters participants. Hence, it can be said that social media is more cost effective for political actors to communicate than traditional media advertising which allows them to reach specific target audiences. From social media, the people can become more political. It is because the political information is more available to citizens and they can participate in discussion with ease irrespective of their geographical locations. Therefore, social media also helps to facilitate more engagement from groups who may not have access to traditional methods of political communication. For example, sharing, reposting and forwarding can disseminate information very quickly.

The algorithms of social media platforms can also be a big factor in the transmission of misinformation. These algorithms tend to favour content that can evoke intense emotional responses and high engagement among the platform's users. As a result, the sensational political information might be displayed more instantly than accurate but less interesting information. This will cause the platform's users to get more fake information through the algorithms system of the social media which will affect the voter's perspective especially the younger voters who

do have much accurate knowledge about the election and the political campaign. The impact of misinformation can be severe during the election season. The incorrect information can shape the perceptions of voters which will confuse them about the political issues and lose the trust in democratic institutions. Hence, the phenomenon of election misinformation has emerged as one of the grand challenges for democratic societies in the digital age. The link between social media and election underscores the need to ensure ethical communication between the political actors and the citizens of media platforms. The accurate and reliable dissemination of information to the voter is vital to democratic in order to maintain the democratic integrity and informed public participation.

Media Ethics And Digital Communication In Election

The ethical communication basically focuses more on the accountability and the accuracy of the digital media. This is especially relevant in a democratic context where the citizens rely on trustworthy data to be able to get a sense of the issues of the political and social concern. Media ethics was traditionally concerned primarily with journalists and the media organizations. Some of the journalists were expected to check facts before printing, report balance and refrain from unnecessary harm to individuals or communities. Professional ethical codes were created to make sure that the media will carry out their duties towards the people. Digital media has opened up a range of ethical issues for more than just professional journalists. In today's world, the political actors and the content creators including the citizens are all involved in the creation and dissemination of information. This definitely shows that ethical communication is fully on the role of the new digital media. While if the information is false and spread on the Internet, it can affect the public opinion and decision making of the voter. In this case, social media do not have any system that can edit filters which makes it easier to spread incorrect information to a wide audience. It is showing the term of social media platforms's responsibility and accountability.

Another ethical issue is the question of balancing the freedom of expression with the need to avoid any harm in terms of media ethics. In a democratic society, the freedom of speech is a fundamental right. But the free circulation of misinformation can confuse people, communities

and the democratic system for others. This makes it a continuous challenge for policymakers and platforms companies to decide on how to overcome the misinformation problem without touching the legitimate political expression. At the same time, public responsibility is also an important thing for media ethics. People who produce, share or receive information should think twice about the accuracy of what they are doing. The unverified political content can help to create confusion and misinformation especially during election time when it is crucial to get the right information. Media ethics offers a valuable lens in considering the problem of misinformation in relation to GE15 Malaysia in terms of ethical responsibility.

Election Misinformation In Malaysia

Election misinformation is an emerging problem in Malaysia's political communication landscape. The availability of the Internet and use of social media has been increasing over time and mass media online have become a significant source of political information for many citizens. These platforms enable political involvement and democratic participation but can also allow the dissemination of misinformation and disinformation. As we know that the misinformation in the Malaysia political realm is nothing new. Past elections have shown the increasing impact of the Internet on political discourse and political behaviour. But with the rise of social media, the spread and velocity of misinformation have grown. The information can now be disseminated in a flash to large networks of users which makes it hard for claims to be verified before they have gone too far. This was especially apparent in the 15th General Election (GE15) in Malaysia. Digital platforms were utilised for the sharing of political messages and to discuss election related issues with the political parties and the supporters all actively using them. Social media like TikTok were significant in influencing public sentiment and engaging in politics. The platform was popular with young voters so it was a good medium to advertise for politics. In the election period, there was an increase in user generated content and live streams that contained political information. Many users will post political information and for political opinion thus some of the content is unverified. At the same time, the political messages, rumours and unverified information can be spread via group chats on the message media

platforms when on the run up of an election. This will cause the false information to be disseminated through the private communication networks and gain access to many people.

The issues relating to race, religion and royalty are also the sensitive issues of the election. Given the multicultural and multi religious nature of Malaysian society, misinformation about the race and religion in election campaigns can build the misunderstanding, fears and social tensions among the communities. Some of the aggressive citizens will post political information about the 3R content without checking its validity and causing an unhealthy environment during the election process. This reflects the fact that misinformation is not only a technological problem but also a social and ethical communication behavior problem.

Applying The Media Ethic Theories On The National Election (GE15) Malaysia

Ethics Of Care Theory

Ethics of Care can be referred to as promoting the wellbeing of the caregiver and the care recipient in a network of social relationships, thereby ensuring the maintenance of relationships (Sander-Staudt, M. (2024)). The ethics of care is interested in the effects of the decisions on people in particular social relationships unlike the conventional ethical theories which focus mainly on universal rules and consequences. The theory states that one's moral actions should be based on caring and concern for others. The individuals need to think about what they are doing and what effect it might have on vulnerable people and whether their behaviour helps to cause harm or to do good. Basically, it can approach the communicator in communication contexts in order to consider the emotional and social implication of the messages that they produce and disseminate beyond the personal interests of the communicator. This theory is directly related to political communication where elections are primarily made up of communication with various

social, cultural and religious backgrounds. Political messages can impact public opinion and social harmony. Hence, the communicators must make sure that the messages they put out do not cause unnecessary fear and hostility.

TikTok Content With Racial And Religious Misinformation During GE15 Malaysia

A major issue the most concern on TikTok is about the ethnoreligious content. Dzamira Dzafri. (2022, November 22) reported that some political material featuring the racial and religious issues shaped the perception of voters. Some videos were designed to suggest that political opponents were a threat to a certain ethnic or religious group while some of them used fear words to mobilize support based on emotional response but not on the real facts. The election saw racially charged content that was being increasingly shared on TikTok according to the media reports after the election. Some non-polite media users posted videos about the historical events in Malaysia and content which seems to incite hatred against specific ethnic groups. There were posts reportedly threatening violence and other peddling false issues about political outcomes and ethnic dominance. At the same time, some posts were also claimed to be coordinated and paid for via partnerships. Race talk was also the top political topic on most social media during the election period. The press comments on online forums showed the increasing worries of the polarization of races in the election. There were fears by many users that political issues on the basis of race and religion were leading to a rise in social media and that communities were starting to see each other as political threats, not citizens.

Analysis

The theory basically focuses on the healthy social relationship and protecting the vulnerable communities. Malaysia is a nation which embraces a multicultural society of various ethics and religious groups. If misinformation is based on race or religion, it can lead to stereotypes and the mistrust in a decline of social cohesion. This is why content based on historical trauma and ethnic tensions are in direct opposition to these principles as it comes at the

price of political influence and not social harmony. This can help to cause fear and anxiety for communities who feel that they are targeted by such content. The material does not promote any constructive dialogue in a democratic context but rather may give the risk beyond the election period. In this context, the damage of misinformation is not prohibited to political consequences to social trust and the community relations among the digital media platforms. Hence, before disseminating potentially politically sensitive information, the communicators should take these social implications into account. The theory suggests that ethical communication should be sensitive to others' experiences and vulnerabilities which racially charged content creators may see as political expression. This definitely means that the communicators are missing the mark in showing care and empathy for responsible political communication.

The Social Responsibility Theory

According to Communication Theory. (2014, July 10) noted that the concept allows for free press but also demands public debate regarding the role of the press and allowing any responsibilities from professional or public interference. There should be freedom of the media but also accountability and responsibility of the society. The channels of communication have a powerful impact on public opinion and a responsibility to present true, accurate and balanced information. While many organizations should not take those solely for political, commercial or personal goals based on the theory but rather should be in the public interest. Communicating with the public must be verified, reliable and helpful to democracy. If wrong or misleading information is spread, this can have a detrimental impact on the quality of public decision making. The concepts of the Social Responsibility Theory are not limited to just traditional media organisations in today's digital age. The information is spread across social media platforms by political actors, influencers and even by ordinary citizens. Thus, it is not only in the hands of journalists to maintain an ethical information environment but also of other stakeholders.

Viral False Misinformation Of Political Election GE15

Based on the Kalbana Perimbanayagam. (2022, November 9) reported a viral post in social media during GE15 saying that voters had to sanitise their hands after putting their fingers into the indelible ink in the voting process. The message said alcohol based sanitisers might render the ink to get dissolved and might have an impact on the voting process. The spread of the message on the Internet led to confusion on the part of the voters about the authenticity of the validity of the new way of voting process. Later, the Election Commission (EC) clarified the information was all false and there was no such requirement. The Election Commission (EC) called on the general public to refrain from dissemination of unconfirmed messages and also called on voters to trust on official election information only. At the same time, the growing popularity of TikTok during GE15 has also raised concerns about misinformation which makes it one of the most influential political communication platforms. TikTok has responded by stating that political parties and regular users will face sanctions after posting misleading political content which includes content deletion and account ban. TikTok also announced that information would be moderated to make sure the posted content does not include any misinformation, hate speech or harmful political content during the election season. The users are allowed to report any violence content about the election on the TikTok platform.

Analysis

This incident is a reflection of the impact of irresponsible information sharing from the point of view of Social Responsibility. The people who spread the message did not check to see if it was true or not before they went viral. This led to misinformation and unnecessary voter confusion in a fast moving manner. The theory noted that the communicators should work in the public interest and provide accurate information. National election periods are very important as citizens rely on accurate information when engaging in democratic activities. This spreading of false election procedures could cause untrust and lead to confusion among the voters communities. Users of ordinary citizens who share information online also have ethical responsibilities. They must verify the information before sharing to others in order to prevent fake information from being spread widely.

The social media platforms serve the same purpose now as they identify what is visible and what is taken away. From this incident, TikTok's moves can be seen as an effort to strike a balanced freedom of expression while also recognizing the need to safeguard the public from harmful misinformation. The case is also an example of how platforms are getting harder to be neutral during national elections. In the term of the theory, the platforms should take a significant role on the cases which pose a risk to democratic participation or public community. The TikTok in this case marks the significance of preventive actions as opposed to reactive responses. The moderation policies can be used to minimise potential harms and contribute to a healthier information environment for voters before misinformation is spread quickly on the digital medi platforms.

Initiatives By Government And Malaysian Communication And Multimedia Commission (MCMC) For Combating Fake News Of National Election

TheEdge. (2022, November 24) reported that during the GE15 campaign period, the Malaysian Communication and Multimedia Commission (MCMC) with the Royal Malaysia Police (PDRM) will actively monitor misinformation. During the run up to elections, the volume of fake news is likely to rise and urged people to check before sharing any information online through social media. The media was also urged to apply fact checking tools like **Sebenarnya.my** in analysing the identity of the suspicious content or any unverified information. The Ministry of Communications (MCM) also set up a Special Task Force comprising over 100 staff from both the MCM and the PDRM to monitor and act against misinformation during the entire election period. The task force was empowered to take action when harmful misinformation was identified online. After the election, MCMC said it had removed more than 100 proactive online posts with the help of digital platforms like TikTok and Instagram. There has been a reduction in the dissemination of fake news and online misinformation since the end of the campaign period.

Analysis

The efforts of MCMC and other government institutions indicate the particle implementation based on the principles of social responsibility at the institutional level. Hence, the public institutions have the important roles to ensure that the citizens are safe from harmful misinformation especially during the elections when the citizens and the democratic are on the line. According to the theory, the communication systems should make a positive contribution to society. This is consistent with the government's work to keep track of the misinformation and provide the fact checking resource in order to help to enhance the quality of information and minimize public confusion. But the rising level of regulation may also create the concern about freedom of expression but it still has the potential to reduce the misinformation on the digital media platforms. So, it is necessary to have a balance between the society against misinformation and ensuring democratic freedoms. It is a social responsibility of communication on media ethics to have an open political debate on the democratic participation.

The Kantian Ethics

Kantian Ethics refers to moral principles which in all conditions and places apply to all people which are free and morally correct in categorical imperatives (Schmidt, J. (2025)). Basically, the theory took the position that there are actions that are right or wrong and that is not the case that an action can only be determined to be good or bad by what it achieves. It is important to talk about the truth among the communicators on social media. The principle of honesty is a universal moral principle because people need information and rationality in order to make decisions. Individuals must be treated as independent decision makers and not be used for one's own personal, political or economic interests. The principle has special significance in the field of political communication as voters rely on accurate information for their democratic decision making. In this theory, it can offer a valuable meaning to consider whether the communication practices are respectful of citizens' right to be told the truth regarding election misinformation. The dissemination of misinformation whether for the benefit of a political party or candidate may be considered unethical if it is done with the intention to affect the voters' attitudes to or behaviour in voting.

False News And Rumours About The Political During GE15 Malaysia

Throughout GE15, SHAH, A., & ISKANDAR, I. M. (2022, October 27) reported that the Malaysian authorities have warned the public multiple times regarding the spreading of false and misleading information about the election. There was significant media coverage often posted of misleading social media posts which aimed at shaping public perceptions of political parties and candidates. Citizens were urged to check information with the official sources before posting on social media. Since the GE15, the rumour on coalition talks and government formation have been rife in social media platforms. There were many rumours going around as to who would be a part of the next government and who would not. As political negotiations continued, several reports turned out to be misleading information.

Analysis

In a democracy, citizens who vote in elections depend on information to access political candidates and the political campaign. The people who received the fake information will get loose on making the informed decisions. Hence, this theory stated that moral action should be guided by moral principles. Hence, it is impossible to accept lies as an acceptable communication strategy since it is a violation of universal principle to truthfulness. When many people who disseminated coalition rumours may not have been trying to mislead others. But the theory does not focus on the intentions of the individual. It is important for one person to confirm the information before sharing it with others. Otherwise, it can help to spread misinformation and to prevent public discussion which is based on facts. The citizens can have false opinions based on false information which can cause poor quality decision making in the democracy.

Utilitarianism Theory

Utilitarianism Theory actually means that the best method of distinguishing between right and wrong is to examine the consequences of decisions and actions (McCombs School of Business. (2025)). Since the theory states that the moral worth of an act should be assessed based on its result. Actions that create the most benefits for the most people are generally morally acceptable, actions that create more harm than benefits are morally unacceptable. This theory requires decision makers to consider what may be good or bad as a result of their decisions prior to deciding whether it is ethically appropriate. This theory can be used on misinformation to determine its overall social effects in the realm of political communication.

TikTok's Management Of Election Misinformation

Hakim, A. (2022, November 3) reported that TikTok has announced in GE15 that it will be stepping up its action against political misinformation on the platform. Politicians and the regular users who spread false or misleading information about politics repeatedly may be removed from the content or restricted in the account. TikTok also joined forces with fact checking in order to enhance the content moderation about the election of misinformation. These ranged from monitoring the content posted online to ensure they check information through official channels so that they will not be confused with harmful misinformation. Sometimes misinformation about race and religion definitely affected the election period among the citizens. By minimizing the misinformation on social media platforms, it can enhance the quality of information and not affect the voter's opinion on the election process.

Analysis

From the theory, TikTok's move makes sense as it wants to do as little harm as possible to the general public. Election misinformation can mislead voters and cause confusion in democratic institutions. Without action, misinformation can reach millions of users and the downside can impact election results. This could limit some users from publishing information as they due to content moderation. Under the theory, restricting the misinformation can prevent many more citizens from being confused. Thus, it is likely that the advantages of moderation more than the disadvantages to a minority of users whose material is being removed. Hence,

TikTok has a positive impact and can help to create a healthier information environment where citizens can access more reliable political information with less misinformation. This helps to ensure good choices are made and improves participation in democracy that will bring positive outcomes for society.

Recommendations

Improving Media Literacy Of The Citizens

Media literacy education is an effective way to address election misinformation. Media literacy is the ability to access and produce media with a critical approach. These skills are crucial in the digital age as citizens are constantly crowded with multiple sources in the social media platforms. There are numerous examples of misinformation that are shared when someone provides information without checking for its validity. Hence, citizens should be encouraged to critically assess the information they received before reposting or forwarding information. It is because they should be able to identify the credible sources between the true information and personal perspectives. Not only that, the educational institutions also have their role on how to educate the citizens on media literacy. Digital literacy and critical thinking skills should be part of the educational curriculum. It is because these skills will help young people to be more responsible consumers and producers of information at an early age. For example, there can be public awareness campaigns on how risky misinformation can be confusing to the citizens. These are the programs that could help to build an awareness culture that can withstand misinformation in election seasons.

The Responsibility Of Social Media Platforms

The social media platforms' responsibilities are to be improved. Social media has a critical role in political communication and in the consumption of information. Hence, they are ethically on duty to limit misinformation and ensure freedom of expression. At the same time, platforms should enhance their fact-checking mechanisms and work in cooperation for the fact checkers to determine what is misleading. If the false information is identified, the internet platforms can give warnings or links to the trusted sources. These measures can highly empower the media users to make informed decisions about content they encounter online. Not only that, there also needs some transparency in algorithms used to recommend content on social media platforms. More transparency about the selection of content on users' feed. This could decrease any sensational content on the media platforms due to the engagement algorithms. The content moderation must meet the standards of freedom of expression but online platforms must also be aware of their duty to reduce the harmful content that can give the false political information.

Enhancing The Ethical Political Communication

The role of political actors has a direct impact on the public opinion and it has a lot of ethical responsibilities. Political parties and candidates should ensure that their communication practices are based on principles of honesty and accountability. Some efforts such as campaign strategies in order to avoid misinformation and manipulation could be engaged in policy discussion and public issues. Hence, public actors should refrain from any unverified information and should take action to fast check the inaccurate information when it occurs. The political parties should also have their own principles of ethical use of digital campaigning. It is because these guidelines can help that campaign activities are consistent with democratic values and those of fair communication. Therefore, an action that creates a context for ethical political communication can help to foster healthier discussion in democracy and increase the public's confidence in political institutions.

Conclusion

The rapid development of social media has changed the way people communicate politically in Malaysia as it has provided opportunities for information dissemination and public engagement. In the context of Malaysia's Fifteenth General Election (GE15), social media has emerged as a crucial platform for disseminating information about politics and communicating with voters. As use of digital communication continues to grow, it helped spread election misinformation as well. This study focuses on the election misinformation from the perspective of media ethics in GE15. The results show evidence of misinformation in the term of political rumours and social sensitivity to the public. During the elections, this kind of information became more visible due to the speed at which it can be shared through social media. This study also concluded some ethical issues regarding the accountability and truthfulness from the election misinformation. By using the media ethic to analyze the national election incident news during the election time. Not only that, the study also provides the recommendation to overcome the issue of election misinformation. It is important to have solutions to deduce any fake news on social media.

Election misinformation is one of the biggest problems that democratic communication has in the digital age. The ethical norms like accountability and media responsibility become more relevant as social media is an important tool in shaping public opinion on political issues. It will be crucial to promote responsible media ethics in communication and to develop media literacy in order to safeguard democratic participation. This allowed the future national election to take place in a more informed and ethical communication framework.

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